

Size Distribution and Elemental Analysis of Fine Particles from Li-ion Battery Cell Fire

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Abstract

This study focuses on the analysis of fine particle emissions from fires of cylindrical lithium-ion battery cells (standard 18650) of two distinct chemistries, namely NMC and NCA. The cells are subjected to thermal abuse in a sealed testing chamber until thermal runaway occurs. The explosion and fire lead to the release of aerosol particles, which are captured using a 14-stage cascade impactor. The range of sizes of the collected fine particles is from 14 nm to 9.7 μm , with the mass mode diameter between 152 nm and 377 nm. Subsequent analysis of each stage filter of the cascade impactor utilizes atomic absorption spectrometry to ascertain the elemental composition of the particles. Lithium and sodium are subjected to further analysis using atomic emission spectrometry. Among the 11 analyzed elements, lithium exhibits the highest concentration in particles smaller than 1 μm , while nickel is predominant in particles larger than 1 μm . Other major elements detected in the particles include aluminum, cobalt, and copper, consistent with the initial composition of the battery cells. Subsequent analysis of particle morphology and elemental composition is facilitated by scanning electron microscopy and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy.

Keywords

particles, fine particles, size distribution, li-ion battery, AAS, AES, SEM, cascade impactor

Introduction

Electromobility has emerged as a prominent representative of environmentally friendly transportation in recent years. Electric vehicles have high engine efficiency in comparison to internal combustion engines and generate zero tailpipe emissions. Despite the significant potential of electromobility, numerous unresolved issues remain, such as electricity production, the availability of rare materials, and the production of batteries. The growing demand for electric vehicles highlights the increasing importance of lithium-ion battery safety. While these batteries enable advanced technology, they also pose significant risks, particularly during thermal runaway events that can lead to fires or explosions. The fire of lithium batteries emits elements that are hazardous to human health, including cobalt, aluminum, copper, and lithium. Fine particles released during such incidents present substantial health hazards when inhaled into the lower respiratory tract.

In the event of an accident or malfunction of a battery cell, thermal runaway (TR) may occur. The initiation mechanisms of TR are electrical, mechanical, or thermal abuse [1], [2]. Electrical damage occurs after overvoltage, overcurrent, overcharge, over-discharge, or short circuit [3]. Thermal initiation of TR occurs after local overheating, or extreme cold [4]. Overheating can lead to the vaporization of the liquid electrolyte, resulting in the formation of gas [5]. Damage to the separator can result in the cathode and the anode of a battery cell becoming electrically connected, leading to strong exothermic reactions [6], [7]. TR is an immediate and uncontrollable process that increases inner pressure and decreases electrolyte stability. A significant amount of heat is generated, causing the temperature of the surface of a battery cell to rise to 400 °C [8], [9]. Furthermore, the sparks generated during an explosion may reach the temperatures of up to 1200 °C [10]. The intensity of TR is dependent on state of charge (SOC). When a battery cell is fully charged, the reaction is significantly more intense compared to a battery cell with a low charge [11], [12], [13]. Due to the TR of a single battery cell, there is a high risk of fire propagation to other cells [14], [15].

The process of TR has the potential to result in the occurrence of fire and explosion, releasing smoke into the atmosphere. The composition of the smoke is a mixture of gaseous and particulate matter, including solid and liquid particles. These particles contain a mixture of elements and substances, such as heavy metals [10]. The release of gas can be attributed to three primary mechanisms: electrolyte decomposition, the reaction between anode and electrolyte, or the decomposition of cathode materials [10] and binders [16], [17]. A comprehensive analysis of the gaseous toxic substances was conducted by Wang et al. [10] and Zhang et al. [18]. The composition of the gaseous emissions primarily consists of CO₂, CO, H₂, H₂O, hydrocarbons, and other substances, depending on the composition of the cathode material. These substances include highly toxic gases such as HF, PF₅, and POF₃ [2]. In addition, Nedjalkov et al. [19] identified the presence of benzene, toluene, styrene, and biphenyl.

The released stream of gases contains approximately 17 % by mass of solid particles of various sizes [8]. In a heterogeneous aerosol environment, complex processes of nucleation and particle growth take place, which are schematically depicted in Fig. 1 as described below. The emission of particles may occur directly into the atmosphere or via firefighter water [8]. It has been observed that nearly 90 % of the total particles, including settleable particles, by weight, are smaller than 500 μm [20]. Particles larger than 100 μm are predominantly formed from the disintegration of the electrodes and the separator. These particles are characterized by a significant settling velocity, resulting in a relatively short persistence in the atmosphere [21]. When the gas stream carrying particles is directed toward a solid surface, impaction leads to particle deposition on the surface.

Particles smaller than 100 μm create a polydisperse aerosol that rapidly fills the entire volume of the test chamber. The smallest particles, known as ultrafine particles, are typically up to 100 nm in size. These particles are formed as molecular clusters, mainly during the initial phase of vapor condensation (nucleation) [22]. Ultrafine particles do not sediment. They are carried by airflow (advection) and are subject to intense dispersion due to the turbulent flow [22]. Molecules in the surrounding medium are in constant Brownian motion, colliding with the particles. Under these conditions, particle movement is influenced by diffusion, which is the primary transport mechanism over short distances for particles smaller than 0.1 μm [23]. These particles possess a higher surface-area-to-volume ratio, which facilitates their inhalation into the respiratory system.

A characteristic behavior of ultrafine particles is their tendency to agglomerate into larger entities by a process called coagulation [9], [24]. The interaction between two particles of smaller size leads to the formation of a larger particle through the interplay of van der Waals adhesive forces and electrostatic forces. The rate of coagulation increases with higher particle number concentrations and higher turbulence intensity in the flow. The process of particle growth is further enhanced by the additional condensation of vapors onto particle surfaces. As the size of the particles increases, gravitational effects become more pronounced, leading to an increase in settling velocity. Changes in ambient relative humidity can alter the moisture content of the particles, affecting their mass and potentially their size [25]. Additionally, particles may undergo fragmentation processes. This process of fragmentation can be initiated by collisions between larger particles that possess sufficient momentum, due to centrifugal forces during periods of intense rotation, or as a consequence of vibrations [22].

Fig. 1 Scheme of particle processes during thermal runaway

A limited number of studies dealt with the size distribution of particles emitted during battery cell fires including the elemental composition of these particles. Zhang et al. [18] studied the elemental composition of settleable particles according to their size ranging from 0.85 mm to 8 mm. Li et al. [20] sorted particles by four sieves of size between 54 μm and 500 μm with the peak size between 100 μm and 300 μm . It was observed that the majority of the particles did not exhibit a spherical morphology [20]. Li et al. [11] observed a positive correlation between the SOC and nickel content, on the one hand, and the median particle size, on the other. The majority of the experiments were conducted on fully charged battery cells. Mao et al. demonstrated a correlation between the lithium content in particles and the SOC of a battery cell [26]. Wang et al. [10] used inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) for elemental analysis of particles with size below 500 μm to detect Ni, Cu, Zn and Cr. The elements predominantly detected in particles from fires of battery cells with lithium nickel manganese cobalt (NMC) oxide cathodes are carbon, nickel, cobalt, aluminum, lithium, or fluorene [18]. Premnath et al. [27] measured the size distribution of fine particles following overcharge and nail penetration of NMC battery cells. The highest number of particles emitted was between 20 nm and 100 nm.

The morphology of particles from battery cell TR can be categorized into three primary types: fragments of the anode or cathode, microspheres, and nanoparticles [24]. Microspheres are predominantly composed of nickel, aluminum, carbon, fluorene, and oxygen [24].

Other research in the field includes the study of temperature-related phenomena, such as spark detection, the design of capture systems, and the development of protective equipment against fine particle emissions [11]. The limited number of studies published on the elemental composition of particles in relation to their size distribution is evident [8], [18], [28], [20]. However, the majority of these studies deal with the elemental composition of particles only in non-respirable fraction of particles. The knowledge about the elemental

composition of fine particles is missing. Consequently, the present study aims to address this knowledge gap by focusing on the elemental composition of particles in the respirable fraction of aerosol particles. That corresponds to particle size from 14 nm to 10 μm with the main focus on particles smaller than 1 μm .

Methods

Two variants of standard cylindrical 18650 lithium-ion battery cells were utilized in the experimental setup. The technical characteristics of both battery cell variants are shown in Table 1. The cathode chemistries of the battery cells were Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) for LGDBHG21865 (No. 1) and Lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA) for Sony Murata US18650VTC5A (No. 2), with the nominal capacity of 3.0 Ah and 2.6 Ah, respectively. The cathodes were extracted from the battery cells and their surface was analyzed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS). The detailed elementary composition of the cathode materials is presented in Table 2. Lithium was not measured by EDS but is also a component of the cathode. It is notable that both battery cells exhibit the highest concentrations of nickel and cobalt. The most significant difference in composition is observed in the presence of manganese. The analysis further revealed the presence of zirconium, with concentrations of 1.5 % in battery cell No. 1 and 0.8 % in battery cell No. 2. This suggests that the zirconium was incorporated as a dopant in zirconium oxide form. The presence of phosphor and fluorine indicates the electrolyte residue. All the battery cells utilized in the experimental setup were fully charged. Each battery cell was subjected to a controlled heating process using an external heat source until a thermal runaway was triggered. The battery cells were arranged in a vertical orientation, with the safety valve positioned towards the top.

Table 1 Technical characteristics of battery cells

Battery cell	Chemistry	Nominal voltage (V)	Nominal capacity (Ah)	Mass (g)	Energy density (Wh/kg)
No. 1	NMC	3.6	3.0	45	240
No. 2	NCA	3.6	2.6	47	199

Table 2 Cathode material of battery cell composition by EDS

[Wt. %]	C	O	F	Al	Si	P
No. 1	8,7	1,7	0,2	0,8	0,1	0,2
No. 2	11,9	2,1	0,7	1,6	0,1	0,6
[Wt. %]	S	Mn	Co	Ni	Sr	Zr
No. 1	0	4,4	11,2	70,9	0,4	1,5
No. 2	0,2	0	12,6	69,5	0	0,8

The heating of battery cells was conducted within a sealed testing chamber, with a volume of 200 liters and equipped with a pressure valve, see Fig. 2. The battery cell is clenched by an aluminum heating element measuring 10 mm in thickness, which was attached at the center of the cell. The heating element involves a resistance heating with the power of 40 W. The interior of the testing chamber is continuously exposed to outdoor air through a 10 mm diameter opening equipped with a HEPA filter, ensuring the incoming air remains uncontaminated. This connection maintains the interior of the test chamber at atmospheric pressure throughout the experiments. For the homogenous distribution of particles within the volume of the testing chamber, two fans are placed in both vertical and horizontal directions to mix the air with the particles inside the test chamber. During the TR event, the gas and the particles leave the battery cell in an upward direction along the longitudinal axis of the battery cell, as shows Fig. 1. Big particles are captured on an impaction inflammable

surface to protect the rest of the equipment in the test chamber. Sampling of particles for subsequent analysis is conducted in the upper portion of the test chamber.

The first set of experiments was executed with utilizing of the cascade impactor Dekati HT-DLPI+. This apparatus utilizes 14 impactor stages with polycarbonate foils, systematically sorting particles based on their aerodynamic diameter. The range of captured particles is from 14 nm to 9.7 μm . The size range of the particles trapped on the individual impactor stages is given in Table 3. The foils with captured particles were weighed to determine the size distribution curve regarding the weight of each fraction. Subsequently, the foils with particles were submitted for elemental analysis.

Table 3 The theoretical size range of the particles trapped on the 14 individual floors of the impactor

Stage	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Min size [nm]	0	14.7	30.6	55.2	94.1	152	252
Max size [nm]	14.7	30.6	55.2	94.1	152	252	377
Stage	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Min size [μm]	0.377	0.596	0.938	1.62	2.42	3.62	5.32
Max size [μm]	0.596	0.938	1.62	2.42	3.62	5.32	9.79

In the second set of experiments, a single filter from polycarbonate with a diameter of 37 mm and a pore size of 0.4 μm was utilized for particle capture. The experimental procedure is shown in Fig. 2. The testing chamber inner air with particles is pumped through a cartridge containing the filter. The third set of experiments used a cascade impactor to capture the particles on aluminum foils with a diameter of 25 mm. Subsequent to this, the particles were subjected to a thorough examination via SEM to ascertain their morphology.

Fig. 2 Setup of the experimental methods including particle capture and further analysis

The filters and foils with captured particles from tests 1 – 4 were used for elemental analysis to detect hazardous elements. The analysis of metal content in the samples followed a structured procedure that began with placing each sample foil in a teflon container. Then, a mixture of 9 ml of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and 3 ml of nitric acid (HNO₃), known as aqua regia, was added to the Teflon container. The samples were then subjected to microwave digestion, a process that ensured complete dissolution of the metals. Following this step, the samples were transferred to plastic tubes and stored in a cool, dark place to maintain stability. Na and Li concentrations were measured using a PFP7 Jenway flame photometer based on atomic emission spectrometry (AES). For the analysis of other metals (Al, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, and Pb), an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS) (ContrAA 800) with

electrothermal atomization was used. Samples were diluted according to the estimated concentration of each element and injected into the spectrometer using an autosampler with 20 μl of sample and 5 μl of matrix modifier ($\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ or $\text{Pd}/\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$). To ensure the accuracy and reproducibility of the measurements, three replicates of each sample were obtained.

Table 4 summarizes carried out tests and corresponding analysis used for identification of particle size distribution and elemental composition. A total of six separate TR events tests were carried out.

Table 4 Composition of the tests performed

Test No.	Battery cell	Particle collection	Size distribution	Chemical composition
1	No. 1	cascade impactor	gravimetric analysis	AAS, AES
2	No. 2	cascade impactor	gravimetric analysis	AAS, AES
3	No. 1	single filter	-	AAS, AES
4	No. 2	single filter	-	AAS, AES
5	No. 1	cascade impactor	SEM	EDS
6	No. 2	cascade impactor	SEM	EDS

Results

Particle size distribution

Experiments were conducted on NMC (battery cell No. 1) and NCA (battery cell No. 2) lithium-ion battery cells. In all cases, particles generated during thermal runaway were captured by drawing the contaminated air from the interior of the testing chamber through a tube to the filters. The diameter of the tube is 5 mm, and the length is 50 mm for tests 3, 4, and 300 mm for tests 1, 2, 5, and 6.

During the first set of tests particles from TR were captured by the cascade impactor, followed by gravimetric analysis to derive the size distribution curve of fine particles. The total mass of particles from test 1 was 22.6 mg with a capture time of 3 min and an initial airflow of 10 l/min. Stages 7 to 12, ranging from 152 nm to 2.42 μm , captured a minimum of 2 mg of particles. The maximum mass of 5.42 mg was captured on stage 8, which contained particles from 252 nm to 377 nm. The particle size distribution obtained from the gravimetric analysis is presented in Fig. 3a. The maximum mass concentration recorded in stage 8 was 1045.0 mg/m^3 .

Test 2 captured the mass of the particles 14.2 mg during the 1.5 min capture interval at an initial airflow of 10 l/min. At least 1 mg of particles were captured in stages 7 to 13 ranging from 152 nm to 3.62 μm . The highest mass concentration 940.8 mg/m^3 was identified in stage 7 ranging from 152 nm to 252 nm. The size distribution of particles is presented in Fig. 3b. The distribution of test 2 shows a bimodal distribution of particles with a secondary peak in stage 11. Stage 2 of the particle size distribution was excluded for both tests 1 and 2, due to the inadequate quantity of collected particles.

Fig. 3 Size distribution of fine particles

In another set of tests particles from TR were captured to a single filter by initial airflow of 15 l/min for a duration of 15 min. The mass of captured particles from test 3 was 28.6 mg. A similar outcome was observed in test 4, with a total mass of 29.9 mg.

Elemental composition

Tests 1 and 2 were executed using a cascade impactor. Each size fraction of the particle distribution was analyzed independently. The obtained elemental composition expressed as a percentage of the total amount of detected elements is shown in Fig. 4a for test 3, and in in Fig. 4b for test 4. It should be noted that only size fractions that are relevant are included in the figures. The stages for the capture of the smallest and the biggest particles are not contained due to the small amount of captured mass of the particles. The elements C, H, and O were not measured due to the analytical method used. However, these elements are expected to be a significant part of the particles composition. The analysis reveals a higher concentration of alkali metals (Li and Na) in smaller particles with a size below 500 nm. Conversely, the larger particles, with dimensions exceeding 1 μm , exhibited a higher concentration of heavy metals, with nickel proving to be the most abundant. In most of the samples, Pb and Cd were not detected.

Fig. 4 Elemental composition of fine particles

In the analysis of particles captured by the cascade impactor, the stages with below-limit particles were excluded from the evaluation. To verify that this procedure did not lead to a significant mistake in the results, additional tests were performed. Tests 3 and 4 involved the use of a single silica filter to capture particles of varying sizes. These particles were subsequently subjected to elemental analysis. The obtained results are presented in Fig. 5 in absolute values respectively to the mass of the particles.

The elemental composition of test 3 (Fig. 5a) shows the presence of Ni and Li, with Ni accounting for 19.0% and Li for 10.4% of the total mass. Elements that account for more than 0.5 % of the total composition include Al, Cu, Co, and Mn. Additionally, Na, Fe, Cd, Cr, and Pb were identified. The particles from test 4, as shown in Fig. 5b, exhibited Ni and Li concentrations of 28.9 % and 17.6 %, respectively. Other descended amount of elements are Al, Cu, Co, Na, Mn, Fe, Cd, Cr, and Pb.

Fig. 5 Elemental composition of particles expressed in absolute portions of the mass

Morphology

The morphology of the collected particles was investigated using SEM. The particles utilized for tests 5 and 6 were once again captured through the use of a cascade impactor. The duration of this process was 15 seconds, with an airflow rate of 10 liters per minute, ensuring the formation of a thin layer of particles on the aluminum foils. The SEM images from tests 5 and 6 are displayed in Fig. 6. These images offer insights into the morphology of the particles and the structure of the agglomerates that formed. For the analysis, stages 6 and 14 were utilized. Stage 6 exhibited a size range of 94 nm to 152 nm. Stage 14 ranged from 3.62 μm to 5.32 μm .

It is evident that each stage of the impactor collects particles with distinct morphologies, indicative of the alterations in chemical composition, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Particles measuring below 1000 nm exhibited higher lithium (Li) content, while larger particles contained higher metal content. The images obtained from stage 14 reveal a non-uniform distribution of particles, with smooth spherical particles being juxtaposed against rough

surfaces. The distinct morphology of these particles is attributable to their disparate chemical compositions. Furthermore, particles from the sixth stage demonstrated a propensity for agglomeration, resulting in the formation of plate-like structures. In comparison, the composition of stage-6 particles exhibits greater uniformity than that of stage-14 particles. The particles that were captured during test 6 to stage 14 were also used for EDS mapping by elemental composition. The SEM images, accompanied by the corresponding elemental mapping, are presented in Fig. 7. The distribution of cobalt within the image is evident, indicating its presence across a diverse range of particles. Iron and copper manifested as spherical particles. Nickel, exhibiting the highest elemental concentration, was distributed across a broad spectrum of particles. Aluminum, serving as the foil material, results in the detected part of the image passing through the particles. It is important to note that the color range was automatically scaled for each element. Consequently, individual images can not be compared among themselves in an absolute sense.

The use of EDS was further employed for the determination of the elemental composition of a specific point on a particle, as illustrated in Fig. 7. The size of the particle in question was approximately 10 μm . The particle's formation was attributed to a coagulation process, resulting in its larger size compared to other particles. The EDS analysis revealed that the predominant element is nickel, with a percentage of 56.4%, which aligns with the results obtained through AAS. The elements with the next highest detection rates were carbon, cobalt, and aluminum, with compositions of 13.1%, 10.4%, and 10.3%, respectively. A comprehensive overview of all detected elements and their respective concentrations is provided in Table 5.

Fig. 6 SEM images a) stage 14, test 5; b) stage 14, test 6; c) stage 6, test 5; d) stage 6, test 6

Fig. 7 EDS mapping of particles from stage 14, test 6

Table 5 Elemental composition of a single particle pointed in Fig. 7 from the EDS spectrum

Element	C	O	F	Al	Si	P	S	Cl
[Wt. %]	13,1	1,5	0,5	10,3	4,1	1,3	0,3	0,1
Element	K	Ca	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
[Wt. %]	0,1	0,2	0,1	0,6	10,4	56,4	0,8	0,2

Conclusions

This study focused on the identification of aerosol particles generated during thermal runaway in lithium-ion batteries, particularly those emitted during battery fires. Experiments were conducted on 18650 cylindrical lithium-ion battery cells to simulate thermal abuse, leading to thermal runaway and significant emissions of aerosol particles. The particles were collected using a cascade impactor to determine their size distribution, revealing a concentration peak between 152 nm and 377 nm. Elemental analysis indicated that smaller particles (<0.5 μm) were rich in lithium, while larger particles (>1 μm) contained higher concentrations of nickel.

The chemical composition of the emitted particles, including hazardous elements such as lithium, nickel, aluminum, cobalt, and copper, reflects the original composition of the battery cells. These particles pose significant health risks due to their ability to penetrate deep into the respiratory system. Lithium was predominantly found in particles smaller than 1000 nm, while nickel was most abundant in particles larger than this threshold, highlighting a size-dependent elemental distribution.

Morphological analysis revealed distinct structural characteristics of the particles. Smaller particles (<152 nm) had a uniform composition and plate-like shapes, whereas larger particles (3.62–5.32 μm) exhibited non-uniform composition and diverse morphologies, including rough surfaces and spherical forms, particularly for particles containing iron and copper. Cobalt was found to be widely distributed, increasing its potential health risks. This study emphasizes the importance of understanding the nature, size, and composition of particles released during lithium-ion battery fires. The findings are critical for assessing potential health hazards and developing mitigation strategies to address the risks associated with the widespread use of lithium-ion batteries, particularly in electric vehicles. Further research is essential to investigate the long-term health impacts of exposure to these fine particles and to establish safety measures to reduce emissions during thermal runaway incidents.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lukáš Preisler: Conceptualization, Experiments, Visualization, Writing. **Simona Jonášová:** AAS and AES analysis, Writing – methods of analysis. **Jiří Pospíšil:** Supervision, Resources, Writing – particle motion, review. **Tomáš Sitek:** SEM/EDS analysis, writing - review. **Renata Komendová:** Supervision – AAS and AES analysis.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request

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